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Digital education, digital technologies, online education, didactic functions, software tools, competence, systems.

The scientific and methodological foundations of systemic, activity-based and competence-based approaches to the application of each type of didactic means are highlighted by domestic and foreign scientists. Baranova Yu.Yu. and Perevalova E.A. developed a methodology for using electronic textbooks in the educational process [1]. T.T.Vezirov studied the formation of professional skills of future teachers of mathematics and computer science based on Web technologies [2]. T.G.Vezirov determined the effectiveness of the use of electronic educational resources for the professional training of legal informatics[3]. S.K.Tursunov has developed an increase in the effectiveness of education with the help of pedagogical software tools [4].

The didactic tasks of the training tools serve to form the informational and

DIGITAL LEARNING TOOL — A MEANS OF SOLVING A PROFESSIONAL PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the theoretical and practical foundations of the formation of a form of digital education in universities, the essence of online education, the correct use of available digital means in education. The problems of using digital educational tools in universities are analyzed. Studies, scientific works, experiments of foreign scientists have been studied and analyzed. The problems, shortcomings and achievements in the teaching and organization of the course "Information and communication technologies" in higher educational institutions in the e-learning environment are identified.

professional competence of future lawyers and to carry out independent reflexive conscious actions.

There was a need to use legal information and search engines as a tool for the formation of information and professional competence of future lawyers. The problem of the development of information and professional competence of future lawyers requires the establishment of scientific and methodological approaches to the formation of reflexive behavior [5]. Psychological and pedagogical factors of self-assessment of one's actions: perception, memory, manifestation and action of will are of great importance for the development of human consciousness. In the mechanisms of interaction of these factors, the didactic functions of educational means are of particular importance.

The elements of the structure of the didactic functions of educational tools: compensatory, adaptive, integrative, motivational, instrumental, informational and interactive serve to develop the ability of future lawyers to independently and creatively carry out their professional activities. Based on the approach to each

element of the structure of the didactic functions of educational means, from the point of view of professionally oriented training, a comparative analysis of the didactic functions of educational means of the traditional and digital educational environment was carried out [6] (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of didactic functions of educational means

Didactic functions of educational tools	An approach in a traditional educational environment	Approach in the digital educational environment
Compensatory	Improving the educational process in a short time with less effort	In the process of education, communication takes place online
Adaptive	Improving the educational process environment	Organization of independent and feedback in professional software
Integrative	The study of the object in its entirety and in parts	The opportunity to work in an electronic educational and methodological environment
Motivational	Awakening (strengthening) interest in knowledge	Through professionally-oriented training
Information	Providing information necessary for the educational process	Availability of all information support in the electronic environment
Instrumental	Provision of activities	Ability to work in information systems
Interactive	Handling of educational resources	Communication within the electronic educational environment

As a result of the analysis of educational tools, the expediency of introducing modern information systems as educational tools in the teaching of the course "Information and Communication Technologies" and the need to create a model of a methodological system of professionally-oriented teaching is substantiated.

Based on the content of teaching the course "Information and Communication Technologies" in the field of legal

education, a methodology has been developed to improve the methodological system of professionally-oriented teaching of the course "Information and communication Technologies" [7], the structure of the formation of information and professional competence, comparative classification of information search systems, a model of formation.

The need for professionally-oriented teaching of the course "Information and Communication Technologies" is

determined by the needs of society, i.e. changes in certain directions, due to the rapid development of information technologies, penetration into every sphere of digital technologies [8].

Effective technologies and legal information retrieval systems have been introduced in such an e-learning environment to form the information and professional competence of future lawyers. Professionally-oriented teaching of the course "Information and communication Technologies" by the method of professional orientation includes the study of practical aspects of the use of ICT in a specific field of activity. The purpose of such training is to analyze the subject area "information and communication technologies" by terms, to set and solve tasks focused on the profession with the help of modern information retrieval systems, devices and software.

In order to develop information and professional competence in the professionally-oriented training of future lawyers, an improved electronic training manual has been created as an element of the environment of legal information search systems. In the electronic educational and methodological complex for the use of legal information and search systems, methodological recommendations, the development of classes, the possibility of learning using interactive methods have been created.

In order to form information and professional competence through the professional training of future lawyers in the e-learning environment, an improved electronic educational and methodological complex was created as an element of the legal information search engine environment. The electronic educational

and methodological complex revealed methodological recommendations on the use of legal information and search engines, the development of lessons, the possibility of learning using interactive methods used in teaching [8].

The electronic educational and methodological complex has integration to legal information and search engines, and the search section of the complex contains regulatory and legal documents. The electronic educational and methodical complex consists of two parts. In the first part, the Curriculum, lecture text, presentations, handouts, assignments, tests, glossary, foreign literature and videos for self-study are placed in folders.

For self-study in an electronic educational and methodological complex, each topic is highlighted separately, and there is an opportunity to access all information on this topic from one window. Practical tasks were developed in a form that promotes the development of thinking, reflexive conscious behavior and creative (creative) abilities. In the electronic educational and methodological complex, you can turn to Legal information and search engines to complete tasks.

As a result of studying the solution of a generalized special legal problem, a didactic synthesis of information and professional competence of future law students arises.

The experimental work was carried out on the basis of a model for the formation of information and professional competence by training in the course "Information and communication technologies" in the direction of the profession.

The results of the experiment determined that the vast majority of the selected contingent did not have the skills and

qualifications to work on a legal problem, and allowed us to conclude that it was necessary to use legal information and search engines in professionally oriented training.

The experimental work carried out in the electronic educational environment showed a high level of knowledge, information and professional competence of the students of the experimental group.

Criteria for assessing the level of knowledge, information and professional competence were developed based on the indicators of the Guilford taxonomy (Table 2).

Table 2. Evaluation criteria based on J.Guilford's taxonomy indicators

Indicators of J.Guilford's taxonomy	Information and professional competence	Evaluation criteria	
		Indicators	
Knowledge	Does not know how to apply previous knowledge when solving a problem	0-55%	Reproductive
Memory	Creating a model for finding a solution to a problem	56-70%	Productive
Divergent thinking	Drawing up an algorithm for solving the problem	71-85%	Partially-search engine
Convergent thinking, evaluation	Comparison of systems and optimal choice of solution	86-100%	Creative

Gilford's taxonomy focuses on knowledge, memory, divergent thinking and convergent thinking.

These indicators were used to correctly assess the step-by-step solution of variable tasks of professionally-oriented training aimed at the formation of information and professional competence.

Based on the conclusions, the necessity of optimizing the possibilities of integrative synthesis of information and communication technologies and the content of professional education in the

formation of information and professional competence of future lawyers is substantiated.

The qualimetric assessment levels adapted to improving the quality of education with the generation of professional processes of readiness for the implementation of professional activities (sociability, design, criticality, creativity) through professionally-oriented training are determined, criteria (reproductive, productive, partially squeaky, creative) and indicators are also developed.

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